

GHR SST

*Group for High Resolution
Sea Surface Temperature*

Summary of the Joint Workshop of the DV-WG, HL-TAG, ST-VAL, and EARWiG on Tropical Warm Pool and High Latitude SST Issues

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The successful workshop was held at the Bureau of Meteorology Head Office, Melbourne, Australia, Monday 5th – Friday 9th March 2012. Thanks are due to the excellent organization of Helen Beggs (Joint Workshop organizer), Gary Wick (Chair of the DV-WG), Jacob Hoeyer (Chair of the HL-TAG), Gary Corlett (Chair of the ST-VAL), Andy Harris (Chair of EARWiG) and Chris Merchant (Chair of CDR-TAG).

It was scientifically a very stimulating meeting. Two days of plenary sessions were followed by two days of collaboration on identified issues by sharing data, code and ideas, and a final day for drawing conclusions and for determining the next actions. The main contributions came from the GHRSSST groups DVWG and HL-TAG, with cross-cutting input from EARWiG, ST-VAL and CDR-TAG.

The aim of the workshop was to achieve progress with the observed and modelled sea surface temperatures (SST) for two regions - the Tropical Warm Pool and high latitudes (particularly in the SH). The Tropical Warm Pool (TWP) region is located in the western tropical Pacific Ocean and the eastern tropical Indian Ocean. Here the ocean shows the highest SST variation per unit area and is one of the most difficult areas to retrieve and validate SST. This is due to a combination of high water vapour amounts, large diurnal warming, frequent cloud cover reducing the amount of SST retrievals from infrared satellite sensors, island chains reducing the spatial coverage of SST from microwave satellite sensors, and a lack of quality *in situ* SST measurements. The High Latitudes (covering the Southern and Arctic Oceans) are challenging regions for measuring SST due to a combination of prolonged cloud cover, large atmospheric variability, variations in sea-ice cover, frontal regions causing high spatial and temporal variability in SST, and a lack of quality *in situ* SST observations for calibration and validation.

User Feedback: The plenary session started with three user talks covering model applications of SST for atmosphere-ocean coupling and flux estimation. The users stressed that diurnal variability is of importance in NWP at 1-15 day time scales (especially relevant for MJO, shallow clouds and convection) and that diurnal variability of SST has non-negligible effects for climate applications. The users want SST_{skin}, SST_{depth} and SST_{foundation}, plus preferably a good model of the diurnal cycle or, alternatively, enough data points to describe the DV profile. The users want to know the DV amplitude at reasonably resolved time and depth and need to know whether the wind fields used in DV modelling are consistent with their application. For matching DV model data to *in situ* and satellite SSTs, it was suggested that GHRSSST evaluates the quality of DV models according to their diurnal warming probability distribution. Five talks were given on various diurnal warming models, followed by further user talks on boundary layer processes and enhanced ocean coupling, as well as radiance assimilation.

In-situ data were discussed – in particular the potential value of different **Argo near-surface** measurements for verification of DV models, for verification of the foundation temperature and for verifying the stability of climate records. Further, the **upgraded drifting buoys** were discussed, and it was highlighted that applications might take into account the time of detachment of the drogue as this influences the depth of the drifter measurement. **Ship measurements**, especially the availability of cruise air-sea flux datasets were discussed. Possible opportunities for GHRSSST in connection with Australia's new research vessel (*RV Investigator*) were presented (e.g. research cruises either into the TWP region or Southern Oceans 2014 and 2015, maybe in connection with other researchers such as the air-sea flux community).

Results of the TWP+ breakout session: The collection of available satellite data in the TWP+ project domain were discussed and extended. Current issues to discuss in EARWiG were identified. An analysis of satellite and buoy diurnal warming differences was linked to diurnal cycles in water vapour distribution and day/night variation in the efficiency of screening sub-pixel clouds. It was decided that the day-night differences of the various satellite instruments and algorithms should be compared, and that consistent SST retrieval algorithms should be employed for day and night in order to avoid the inclusion of implicit inter-algorithm retrieval biases. This way, after a quality assessment and filtering of outliers, MTSAT-1R, AVHRR, AMSR-E and other satellite SST data may be compared with the diurnal variability models in the TWP+ domain. In particular, MTSAT-1R SSTs were assessed for TWP+ applications and improvements suggested. Further analysis is required to ascertain the impact of SST algorithm sensitivity in high water vapour conditions on observed day/night SST differences. Several issues with the TWP+ data set (involving satellite SST and wave model outputs) were identified during and immediately following the workshop. NOAA has recently provided updates to the MTSAT processing code and BoM will reprocess the data ASAP. The TWP+ data set will be updated by the end of March 2012 and changes reported via the GHR SST TWP+ web page and email to the TWP+ collaborators.

The following models were discussed and initial TWP+ results presented: Gentemann (2003), Castro LUT, COARE, Wick modified KC, Zeng-Beljaars (ZB), ZB+T and KC with sea state. Additional DV models discussed for inclusion in TWP+ were POSH v2 and Janssen/ECMWF. Improved land masking was suggested to improve and increase coverage of the microwave measurements. The use of TWP-ICE and IMOS ship air-sea flux data sets were discussed in relation to validation of DV models and possible ingest into DV look-up tables. Chris Merchant presented a new method for testing DV models against day-night difference distributions in satellite SST. Additional direct comparisons of the different models for identified cases of extreme warming have been initiated by Gary Wick and Sandra Castro. Gary Corlett presented results showing the potential of using satellite in situ match-ups at multiple depths (e.g. comparing AATSR SST_{skin} to drifter SST_{0.2m}, GTMBA SST_{1.0m} and Argo SST_{3-5m}) as a useful dataset for testing DV models.

Results of the High Latitude breakout session: The algorithms applied to High Latitudes were reviewed, and algorithm improvement work was initiated concerning the air-sea temperature difference which can be extreme in this region (particularly in the Arctic due to the proximity of continental land masses and concomitant impact on atmospheric temperature & humidity structure), hard-to-spot sea ice and complex clouds with long shadows. The Multi-sensor Matchup Dataset (MMD), which has been developed in the ESA SST climate change initiative project, was demonstrated to be a useful tool for improvements of algorithms and for investigating the origin of the errors. The investigations showed a difference in the SST algorithm performance in the Arctic and Southern Oceans, where daytime Arctic Ocean SSTs have significantly higher uncertainties than daytime Southern Ocean SSTs. This can probably be attributed to differences in atmospheric conditions between hemispheres. The workshop provided new opportunities to build links to the sea-ice community, particularly to the in situ network. Collaborations have been initiated for sea ice analysis intercomparisons and consistency, ice surface temperature in-situ observations (AFIN and Antarctic AWS data), Southern Ocean SST trends and sea ice anomalies.

Summarized WG and TAG activities:

- DVWG is mining the TWP+ data set for improvements to diurnal warming models, and for analysing diurnal warming events as observed by different satellites.
- EARWiG investigated several ideas for IR algorithm improvements in both tropical and high latitude regions, discussed cloud detection, and the potential for MW improvements in connection with land masking.
- HL-TAG discussed the sea ice coverage, its trends and new in-situ measurements of sea ice temperature.
- ST-VAL investigated robust uncertainty estimation, discussed possibilities of homogenisation of quality levels across similar instruments (e.g. for each AVHRR product), and promoted the use of multi-sensor in-situ matchups.
- CDR-TAG has been exploring the information content of observed SST distributions.

The **Agenda of the workshop with links to the presentations** and the abstracts can be accessed via the GHRSSST web-site: <https://www.ghrsst.org/ghrsst-science/Meetings-and-workshops/>.